

CINIE 2023

22TH, 23TH and 24TH March 2023

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID
Avda. Juan de Herrera, 6-28040-MADRID

DEPARTAMENTO DE TECNOLOGÍA DE LA EDIFICACIÓN

CINIE

ABSTRACTS BOOK

LIBRO DE ACTAS

International
Conference of
Educational
Innovation in
Building

*Congreso
Internacional de
Innovación
Educativa en
Edificación*

Escuela Técnica
Superior de
Edificación

CONSEJO GENERAL
DE LA ARQUITECTURA TÉCNICA
DE ESPAÑA

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE EDIFICACIÓN

Avenida Juan de Herrera, 6. 28040 – Madrid

Tel. 913367595 Fax: 91 336 76 44

Organizador: Departamento de Tecnología de la Edificación de la ETSEM.

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Depósito Legal : M-6773-2023

VIRTUAL REALITY AS A LEARNING METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGN STUDENTS 1

Alejandra Vidales Barriguete, Mercedes Valiente López, Patricia Aguilera Benito, Carolina Piña Ramírez, Manuel Álvarez Dorado, Alicia Zaragoza Benzal, Tomás Gil López, Pedro Palmero Cabezas, Isabel Bach Buendía

INNOVATIVE EXPERIENCE OF YOUNG RESEARCHERS TEACHING TECHNICAL SUBJECTS IN ARCHITECTURE DEGREE 3

Manuel Alejandro Pedreño-Rojas; Emilio Romero-Sánchez; María Victoria Requena-García-Cruz

NEW METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH IN BUILDING MATERIALS SUBJECTS FOR ERASMUS STUDENTS 5

Marta Rodríguez-Aybar; Manuel Alejandro Pedreño-Rojas; César Porras-Amores

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE APS METHODOLOGY WITH BUILDING STUDENTS TO SEEK NEW WAYS OF REVALUING END-OF-LIFE TYRE WASTE 7

Alicia Zaragoza Benzal; Daniel Ferrández Vega; Jorge Pablo Diaz Velilla; Rafael Marcos Sánchez

APPLICATION OF DESIGN THINKING IN THE CLASSROOM TO MEET THE CHALLENGES OF SUSTAINABLE BUILDING DEVELOPMENT 9

Alicia Zaragoza Benzal; Daniel Ferrández Vega; Alberto Leal Matilla; Manuel Álvarez Dorado

EVALUATING ECO-MATERIALS IN THE ACTIVE CLASSROOMS OF THE MATERIALS INNOVATION SUBJECT 11

Álvaro Alonso Díez; Raquel Arroyo Sanz; Alba Rodrigo Bravo; Lourdes Alameda Cuenca-Romero; Sara Gutiérrez-González; Verónica Calderón Carpintero.

<i>A PROPOSAL FOR IMPROVING MATHEMATICS TEACHING IN ARCHITECTURE AND ENGINEERING</i>	83
<i>María José Pereira Sáez; María José Souto Salorio; Ana Dorotea Tarrío Tobar</i>	
<i>PROJECT-BASED LEARNING AND SELF-EVALUATION FOR TRAINING INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERS IN GRAPHIC EXPRESSION</i>	85
<i>María Linares Serrano; Felix Terroba Ramírez; Manuel Gonzalez-Gallego</i>	
<i>MANAGEMENT OF COLLABORATIVE WORK IN ENGINEERING COURSES</i>	87
<i>María Linares Serrano; Gema Gómez-Pozuelo; Miguel Martín-Sómer, Alicia García, Inés Moreno, Arturo Vizcaíno, Gisela Orcajo, Isabel Pariente</i>	
<i>APPLICATION OF ICT AS A METHOD OF MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS</i>	89
<i>Mario González Barriguete; Alejandra Vidales Barriguete; Laura Martínez Badillo; Noelia Sánchez Moreno</i>	
<i>SERVICE-LEARNING FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE MUNICIPAL MARKET OF LA PAZ (MADRID)</i>	91
<i>Marta Echevarría Gómez-Escolar; Jesús García Herrero; Miguel Ángel Gálvez Huerta; María Antonia Fernández Nieto; José Luis Parada Rodríguez; Jorge Gallego Sánchez-Torija</i>	
<i>THE DENIAL OF THE SELF AS A FRAMEWORK FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF HEGEMONIES IN UNIVERSITY EDUCATION</i>	93
<i>Natalia Millán Acevedo</i>	
<i>VIRTUAL REALITY EXPERIENCES FOR LEARNING ABOUT STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOUR</i>	95
<i>Mario Núñez Fernández; Juan Pedro Cortés Pérez; Juana Arias Trujillo</i>	
<i>PROPOSALS FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN GROWTH THROUGH THE CONVERSION OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS AS A VERTICAL TRANSVERSAL LEARNING ACTIVITY OF THE URBAN PLANNING SUB-MODULE</i>	97
<i>Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez; Helena Iballa Naranjo Henríquez</i>	
<i>PROPOSAL OF A PILOT FORMATIVE EXPERIENCE FOR THE SUBJECT TECHNICAL SYSTEMS APPLIED IN THE DESIGN OF A RIGID ORIGAMI KINETIC PAVILION</i>	100
<i>Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez; Fernando Martínez Soto</i>	
<i>SERVICE-LEARNING FOR BUILDING ENGINEERING EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY</i>	104
<i>Patricia Aguilera-Benito; Juan López-Asiain-Martínez; Isabel Bach-Buendía; Mercedes Valiente López; Víctor Sarda Martín</i>	

PROPOSALS FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN GROWTH THROUGH THE CONVERSION OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS AS A VERTICAL TRANSVERSAL LEARNING ACTIVITY OF THE URBAN PLANNING SUB-MODULE.

¹ Pablo Miguel De Souza Sánchez (P. M. De Souza Sánchez); ² Helena Iballa Naranjo Henríquez (H. I. Naranjo Henríquez)

¹ PhD. in Architecture from the UPM. Professor at Universidad Europea de Canarias. pablo.desouza@universidadeuropea.es; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6722-3650>

² PhD. in Urbanism from the UPC and in Geography from the Paris1-La Sorbonne University. Professor at Universidad Europea de Canarias. iballa.naranjo@universidadeuropea.es <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9893-0481>

Keywords: Educational innovation, Human development, Urban planning, Territory, Landscape

Abstract

Through the methodology of a practical case study [1] of experiences of teaching based on projects [2], the learning results achieved in the subjects of the urbanism sub-module are exposed, analyzed, and studied in this research: City Planning from the third course, and City Workshop of the fourth course, both subjects linked to a learning activity with a common statement that follows the methodology of Vertical Workshop [3] and transversal between subjects.

The reclassification of the industrial land of the historic refinery of the CEPSA company located in the city of Santa Cruz de Tenerife (Fig. 1) into residential land, free spaces, public facilities, and tourism program is directly linked to the urban expansion of the city that began in the first decade of the 21st century towards the old neighborhoods of Cabo-Llanos. With what the structural systems projected and proposed by the students had to be established trying to give answers of integration and continuity with the existing axes and solutions to conflicts and problems detected in the previous phase of analysis [4].

Figure 1. Perspectives of the administrative district No. 4 Ofra-Costa Sur with the CEPSA refinery in the foreground and initial proposal of the system of green spaces.

Sources: <https://diariodeavisos.elespanol.com/2022/01/el-desmantelamiento-de-la-refineria-de-santa-cruz-de-tenerife-comenzara-en-marzo/> and <https://www.santacruzdetenerife.es/web/presentacion-santa-cruz-verde-2030>

All the land occupied by the CEPSA refinery makes up most of the Buenos Aires neighborhoods, which is part of the administrative district No. 4 Ofra-Costa Sur (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Administrative districts of Santa Cruz de Tenerife and detail District 4 superimposed on information from Google Maps, and initial proposal for systems of green spaces and road infrastructures. Source: <https://www.santacruzdetenerife.es/web/presentacion-santa-cruz-verde-2030>

Coinciding with the end of the 2021-22 academic year and for it to be taken into consideration in the preparation of the Learning Guides for the 2022-23 academic year subjects, the Universidad Europea defined what it came to call the six pillars of the Academic Model, which were substantiated in the following concepts: Simulated environments, Professional environments, Investigative interest and Data-Driven approach, Integrated Curriculum, Transdisciplinary, and One World.

For the definition of the common lines of the statement, the following were deepened:

The integrated curriculum, which, from a holistic approach, aspires to inclusive and transversal learning of contents, competencies, and learning results, linking the subjects of Integrated Drawing workshops [5] and project design with the submodule of urbanism that allows the student to interrelate knowledge and skills with professional practice.

The data/driven researcher approach encourages decision-making based on objective data extracted by the students themselves in their continuous research work, developing critical and analytical thinking with which to face the search and study of information. The conduct of architectural research outside the limits of the discipline itself is a relatively recent phenomenon, although climate design and the development of building products and systems seem to have been a focal point of research in the fifties, research in architecture and urbanism developed in the 1960s and early 1970s in a wide range of subject areas, including socio-economic issues, sustainable urbanism, design methods and energy consumption [6].

And finally, the third pillar of the academic model on which this activity is based is the so-called One World, in which students are encouraged not only to receive technical academic training, but also a base of values and social, ethical, and environmental commitments [7]. Likewise, this pillar aspires to train students capable of functioning in complex multicultural environments.

References

- [1] P. M. De Souza Sánchez, N. Martínez Martínez, H. I. Naranjo Henríquez, D. Sellet. Las artes plásticas en la mejora del aprendizaje experiencial interdisciplinar. Un acercamiento con estudio de casos y propuestas. In: A. B. Barragán Martín, M. d. M. Simón Márquez, Á. Martos Martínez & M. d. M. Molero Jurado (Eds.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Arte y Humanidades: Experiencias de cambio en la Metodología Docente*. Dykinson S.L. 2022. 123-138 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7493297>
- [2] P. M. De Souza Sánchez, R. Godoy Rodríguez. A.B.P. real de promoción de la arquitectura, el arte y la naturaleza de La Orotava. In: J. Sierra Sánchez & M. Antón Barco (Eds.), *De la Polis a la Urbe a través de miradas interdisciplinares*. McGraw-Hill, 2021, 715-740. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6372910> Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/11268/10900>
- [3] P. M. De Souza Sánchez. Taller vertical y metodología ABP en la realización de proyectos de arquitectura cinética e interactiva con patrones de pliegue estructurales. In: Á. M. Martínez, A. B. B. Martín, M. del Mar Molero Jurado, M. del Carmen Pérez-Fuentes, M. del Mar Simón Márquez, & J. J. G. Linares (Eds.), *Innovación Docente e Investigación en Ciencias, Ingeniería y Arquitectura: Nuevos Enfoques en la Metodología Docente*. Dykinson S.L. 2021. 49-66. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6370857> Handle: <hdl.handle.net/11268/10901> <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv2gz3t8w.6> <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv2gz3t8w.6>
- [4] H. I. Naranjo Henríquez. *Agotamiento del territorio. El caso de Gran Canaria*. [Tesis Doctoral] Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), 2010.
- [5] P. M. De Souza Sánchez, E. Ferrer Román, H. I. Naranjo Henríquez. Innovación metodológica de las actividades de dibujo de la titulación de arquitectura. Revisión del submódulo de dibujo del Grado en Fundamentos de la Arquitectura como adaptación al Espacio Europeo de Educación Superior. *HUMAN REVIEW. International Humanities Review / Revista internacional de humanidades*, 12(3. Monográfico: Proposals for quality higher education / Propuestas para una educación superior de calidad), 2023, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.37467/revhuman.v12.4712>
- [6] P. M. De Souza Sánchez. *El pliegue en la arquitectura*. [Tesis Doctoral], E.T.S. Arquitectura (UPM), 2017. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20868/UPM.thesis.47994>
- [7] H. I. Naranjo Henríquez, P. M. De Souza Sánchez. Learning activities for human development coordinated for the Project Module: Composition, Projects and Urbanism. *6th International Conference of Educational Innovation in Building*, 87–88. 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7589626>